

THE ROLE OF THE MANAGER IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY OF COMPULSORY EDUCATION

Khudoyberdiyev Eldor Uktamjonovich

Doctoral student at the National Research Institute named after A. Avloniy

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Abstract. This article discusses the importance of strategy in the development of general education institutions, the role of the manager in the durable development and implementation of the strategy. The problems of today's school management and their negative consequences on the quality of education are analyzed on the example of the results of the PISA-2022 international assessment research and the questionnaire conducted among the leaders and teaching staff. Also clarified the concepts of strategy and manager.

Keywords: general education institutions, school, development, quality of education, questionnaire, PISA-2022, strategy, director, manager, team, employees.

Introduction. In today's rapidly changing state requirements and society's needs, there is a need to transform schools into institutions capable of meeting these needs. This requires the development of the activities of general education institutions through continuous improvement. Based on this need, if we consider that the development of schools is a purposefully planned process, it is necessary to develop a SMART strategy and give it priority in management. For the school development strategy to be SMART and to implement this strategy together with the team without deviating from the goal, the principal must be a manager.

Materials and methods. As part of our research in this direction, according to the results of a survey conducted among 1417 school leaders and pedagogues, most respondents (58.8%) pointed out the lack of management strategy development and implementation skills of the directors (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Opinions of respondents

It can be seen that such a situation has caused a number of problems in the development of general education institutions, that is, their main function - ensuring the quality of education. For

example, the results of the PISA-2022 international assessment program, in which Uzbekistan participated for the first time, showed shortcomings related to the quality of school education. In particular, Uzbek pupils ranked 72nd among 81 countries in terms of mathematical literacy, and 80th in natural sciences and reading literacy. If we look at the details, more than 80 percent of our pupils' education level does not exceed the 1st level. This means that most of our pupils who participated in the program had a hard time understanding the tasks, let alone completing them. In mathematics exams, only 14% of our pupils showed the result of the 2nd level, only 4% were able to reach the 3rd level and 1% were able to reach the 4th level. Any pupil from Uzbekistan could not record the highest 5th and 6th level results. The results in the areas of natural sciences and reading literacy are not much different. In general, none of our pupils who participated in the program could reach the 5th or 6th level in any direction. By comparison, 41% of pupils in top-ranked Singaporean schools achieved a level 5 or 6 in mathematics [2].
Mathematical literacy results of Uzbek pupils in the PISA-2022 international assessment program

Figure 2. Student levels of mathematical literacy

Result and Discussion. The main goal of developing schools based on the requirements of modern world is to turn them into places of high-quality education, to raise the intellectual potential of pupils to the level of pupils of developed countries, thereby increasing the human capital potential of the country. "Modernization of school education requires not only a fundamental and alternative sense of opportunities, but also well-thought-out strategies that help to achieve changes in education" [7; p. 235].

Strategy is the art of guiding the implementation of a goal, identifying the most important issues and directions in the development of a certain movement, and developing a mechanism for their implementation when accepting a solution for each process situation [6; 54]. It is considered a course aimed at changing the culture of the members of the organization and makes it necessary for the employees of the organization to fulfill several requirements, for example, to act competently, to help and support each other" [1;13]. Also, the strategy is a long-term development mechanism built on the basis of values and modern trends based on the main goal of the organization together with the team under the leadership of the leader. Therefore, based on these features of the strategy, it can be said that it is the most important tool for school development and ensuring the quality of education. This opinion was confirmed by 78.8% of survey participants (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Opinions of respondents

The successful operation of the strategy depends on the school director in every way. Because developing a strategy requires creative and critical thinking from a leader, the ability to listen to and analyze the opinion of the team, the ability to assess the weaknesses and strengths of the institution, the risks, and opportunities in the external environment, and to be a marketer. - to be able to communicate effectively with mothers, to identify the unique abilities and potential of employees, to be able to correctly distribute tasks to them, to avoid transferring a certain part of their powers to lower managers, to work together with stronger people in a team Must have the ability to be fearless, adhere to deadlines, be flexible, exceed promises, recognize even small achievements of employees, motivate them to work on themselves, and create a strong team and a healthy environment. It is also necessary to have legal and financial literacy. Control should be used not as a mechanism of punishment, but as a tool for timely correction of problems and shortcomings in the management process, and at the same time, for evaluating the performance of employees and motivating them based on this.

In modern management, it is emphasized that such characteristics are characteristic of a manager, that the head of the school should be a manager, and that his role in strategy development and implementation is important [3; 1233-1238] and "A manager is a qualified specialist who has received special training and thoroughly mastered the secrets and laws of management" is defined [5; 123].

It is also important that the manager has an important role in the development of educational institutions, he is a leader as well as a skilled manager. Because "...a manager is different from an administrator. He does not rule, he does not give orders, but he leads others. They are not subordinate to him, but followers" [4; 214-215]. Therefore, the team is not afraid of the manager, but rather respects him and unites around him, using all his strength and potential to implement the defined strategy. This ensures the school's competitiveness and efficiency.

Conclusions. Therefore, as we aim to increase the human capital potential of the country by ensuring the quality of education today, it is necessary to train modern managers who will manage the main institution that performs this task - schools.

However, if we aim to improve the quality of education in schools, we cannot do this without a well-developed strategy. It is impossible to develop a strategy carefully and implement it effectively without a good manager. Therefore, we should entrust the management of schools to

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REFERENCES

1. Kattakishiyev B., Mamayusupov I. Strategik menejment. fanidan praktikum. - T., "Fan va texnologiya", 2008. – 13-b.
2. Schleicher A. PISA 2022: Insights and Interpretations. OECD 2023. 68 p.
3. Semir Šejtanić. Strategies for efficient management by school managers at elementary schools. Article *in* International Journal of Advanced Research. May 2017, pp. 1233-1238. DOI: 10.21474/IJAR01/4237#sthash.e0e2a3fI.dpuf
4. Yo‘ldoshev, N.K. Menejment: darslik / N.K. Yo‘ldoshev, G.E. Zaxidov. – Toshkent: – “O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati” nashriyoti, 2018. – 392 bet. 214-215-b.
5. Zayavitdinova N.M. Menejment: o‘quv qo‘llanma / N.M. Zayavitdinova, D.M. Artikova, S.Sh. Xodjiyeva, – Toshkent: “Turon Nashriyot”, 2021. – 160 bet. – 123-b.
6. Қосимов Ғ.М. Менежмент: Олий ўқув юртлари талабалари учун дарслик. Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2002. – 54 б.
7. Шляйхер А. Жаҳон миқёсидаги таълим. XXI аср мактаб тизимини қандай барпо этмоқ керак? / сўз боши Ш.Шерматов, Ҳ.Умарова; Умумий таҳрир Д.Норбоева; таржимонлар: Р.Ахматова, Д.Норбоева. – Тошкент: “Zamin Nashr” nashriyoti, 2022. – 344 б. – 235 б.